

Implantation of A Myval Octacor Aortic Valve in the Pulmonary Position Secondary to Combined Pulmonary Valve Disease Due to Severe Subvalvular Stenosis and Moderate Regurgitation: Case Report

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ABSTRACT

Pulmonary stenosis is a congenital heart disease that may occur in isolation or in association with conditions such as Tetralogy of Fallot and Noonan Syndrome. It may be located at the valvular, subvalvular, or supra-valvular level and is classified as mild, moderate, or severe according to the obstructive gradient. As the disease progresses, it may lead to right ventricular failure, dyspnea, syncope, and systemic congestion. Pulmonary regurgitation is usually secondary to pulmonary hypertension or surgically corrected congenital heart diseases, resulting in volume overload and deterioration of right ventricular function. Diagnosis is primarily established by echocardiography, complemented by cardiac magnetic resonance imaging and cardiac computed tomography. Percutaneous treatment with transcatheter valves, such as Melody, Harmony, and Edwards SAPIEN, has demonstrated improvement in symptoms, reduction of pulmonary regurgitation, and preservation of right ventricular function, although appropriate anatomical selection is required due to the risk of complications.

KEYWORDS: Stenosis, transcatheter implantation, regurgitation, congenital, Myval, replacement.

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I. INTRODUCTION

Pulmonary stenosis is a congenital cardiac defect whose severity may be classified as mild, moderate, or severe, involving the pulmonary valve, the right ventricular outflow tract, or the pulmonary arteries, thereby affecting blood flow from the systemic and cardiac circulation to the pulmonary circulation. Pulmonary stenosis may occur in isolation or in association with various congenital heart defects such as Tetralogy of Fallot, and it may present with supra-valvular or subvalvular obstruction (1). Pulmonary stenosis may also be associated with genetic syndromes such as Noonan Syndrome, linked to mutations in PTPN11, KRAS, SOS1, and RAF1, as well as congenital disorders including tricuspid atresia, complete and corrected transposition of the great arteries, double-outlet right ventricle, and Tetralogy of Fallot (1). Isolated pulmonary stenosis accounts for approximately 7–12% of congenital heart diseases. It is associated in 56% of cases with extracardiac comorbidities and neurodevelopmental disorders in relation to pulmonary

stenosis. Approximately 50% of patients with pulmonary stenosis are associated with PTPN11 mutation and Noonan Syndrome. There is no sex predilection (1). The subtype of subvalvular pulmonary stenosis is characterized by obstruction below the pulmonary valve at the level of the right ventricular infundibulum. It is observed in conditions such as Tetralogy of Fallot and double-chambered right ventricle and is associated in 20–30% of patients with Noonan Syndrome in the context of hypertrophic cardiomyopathy (1). On the other hand, pulmonary valve regurgitation occurs when blood flows back from the pulmonary artery into the right ventricle during diastole. Physiological pulmonary regurgitation, described as a minimal amount of regurgitation, is commonly observed in nearly all individuals, particularly with advancing age.[8] Certain pathological conditions may lead to excessive and clinically significant regurgitation, negatively affecting ventricular function. This type of regurgitation may manifest clinically with symptoms of right-sided volume overload and

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heart failure. Pulmonary regurgitation is usually not the primary pathological process, but rather a secondary finding associated with an underlying condition such as pulmonary hypertension or dilated cardiomyopathy.[8]

II. CASE PRESENTATION

A 63-year-old female patient with a history of Tetralogy of Fallot surgically corrected at 13 years of age and ventricular septal defect closure at 14 years of age, with a medical history of hypertension and hypothyroidism, underwent cardiologic follow-up by the pediatric cardiology service at our center. Echocardiographic evaluation documented severe subvalvular pulmonary stenosis as well as moderate pulmonary regurgitation. She currently presented to the emergency department due to progressive deterioration in functional class over the previous 6 months, characterized by dyspnea on mild to moderate exertion and at rest, as well as one episode of syncope, fatigue, and dependence in performing daily activities, thereby significantly reducing her quality of life. The patient was hospitalized at our institution, and a multidisciplinary Heart Team medical-surgical discussion was conducted, concluding that percutaneous pulmonary valve replacement should be performed. However, the patient presented with post-stenotic dilation of

Figure 1: Implantation of a Myval Octacor Aortic Valve in the Pulmonary Position. A) Myval Octacor 27.5 mm valve.

B. Pulmonary stenosis.

C) Measurements: RV–infundibulum junction 23 mm, subvalvular region 10 mm, annulus 22.2 mm, initial portion of the main pulmonary artery (MPA) 33.7 mm.

D) BeGraft 20 × 48 mm Stent.

III. DISCUSSION

Initially, pulmonary stenosis may be asymptomatic; however, as the disease progresses, patients may develop right ventricular failure and exertional symptoms such as dyspnea, chest pain, and/or palpitations. Advanced cases are

characterized by signs of systemic venous congestion, including jugular venous distention, hepatic congestion, peripheral edema, syncope, or exertional presyncope, secondary to the inability of the right ventricle to maintain and/or increase cardiac output during physical activity (6). In cases of mild to moderate subvalvular pulmonary stenosis, infundibular narrowing produces a systolic murmur that increases during inspiration. As stenosis progresses, the duration of the murmur becomes prolonged and its intensity decreases due to reduced antegrade flow. A left parasternal heave may also be palpable, and an additional systolic murmur may be heard along the left sternal border secondary to tricuspid regurgitation (6). The most frequent electrocardiographic findings are right axis deviation and right ventricular hypertrophy (6). Chest radiography may demonstrate enlargement of the right atrium; another finding suggestive of subvalvular stenosis is the absence of pulmonary artery prominence (6). Multiple imaging modalities are available to detect and classify the severity of this valvular disease, including transthoracic echocardiography, cardiac magnetic resonance imaging (CMR), and cardiac computed tomography (CT) (7). Transthoracic echocardiography is the initial diagnostic strategy, allowing assessment of severity, anatomy, etiology, and associated complications (7). Early findings may include right ventricular hypertrophy. In the short-axis view at the level of the great vessels, narrowing of the right ventricular infundibulum together with turbulence in the right ventricular outflow tract can be identified. In advanced cases, right chamber dilation and tricuspid regurgitation may also be present (6). CMR provides qualitative assessment through anatomical reconstruction of the right ventricular outflow tract, enabling localization of the stenotic site and classification of pulmonary valvular disease severity in cases where echocardiography is insufficient for characterization (6,7). The high spatial resolution of cardiac CT allows anatomical reconstruction of the pulmonary valve and adjacent structures and is considered essential prior to therapeutic intervention (7). The degree of obstruction and severity of pulmonary stenosis can be assessed by echocardiography or transcatheter evaluation and classified as mild, moderate, or severe according to the following parameters: mild stenosis, maximum gradient <36 mmHg; moderate stenosis, maximum gradient between 36 and 64 mmHg; and severe stenosis, maximum gradient >64 mmHg. Regarding pulmonary valve regurgitation, it is most commonly caused by pulmonary hypertension, which leads to dilation of the pulmonary artery and pulmonary valve annulus, resulting in incomplete leaflet coaptation. Other important causes include congenital heart diseases, particularly Tetralogy of Fallot and postoperative states following surgical correction of right ventricular outflow tract anomalies. Less common etiologies include infective endocarditis, carcinoid syndrome, rheumatic disease,

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connective tissue disorders, trauma, and complications secondary to valvotomy or transcatheter interventions. Mild pulmonary regurgitation may also occur physiologically in healthy individuals without structural heart disease [8]. Drug-induced valvular insufficiency has mainly been associated with the use of ergot-derived dopaminergic agonists such as Pergolide and Cabergoline. These medications are associated with an increased risk of cardiac valvular regurgitation due to fibrotic changes and valvular thickening mediated by serotonergic stimulation of 5-HT_{2B} receptors. Although the predominant involvement occurs in left-sided valves, right-sided valves, including the pulmonary valve, may also be affected, resulting in clinically significant valvular insufficiency [9]. Chronic pulmonary regurgitation is a frequent complication in patients with previously repaired congenital heart disease, particularly in those with a history of Tetralogy of Fallot, pulmonary atresia, truncus arteriosus, or Ross and Rastelli procedures. Significant pulmonary regurgitation leads to right ventricular volume overload, promoting dilation and progressive deterioration of right ventricular function, as well as reduced functional capacity, ventricular arrhythmias, and increased risk of sudden cardiac death [10]. Among the principal devices currently used are the Melody Transcatheter Pulmonary Valve and the Edwards SAPIEN Valve, both implanted through a transcatheter approach. Reported studies demonstrate that these procedures significantly reduce pulmonary regurgitation and residual right ventricular outflow tract gradients while improving clinical symptoms, functional class, and hemodynamic parameters [10]. Furthermore, percutaneous treatment helps preserve right ventricular function and delay the need for repeat surgical interventions, a particularly important consideration given that these patients often require multiple procedures throughout their lifetime. Nevertheless, potential complications associated with the procedure have been described, including stent fracture, infective endocarditis, prosthetic dysfunction, conduit restenosis, and risk of coronary compression, highlighting the importance of appropriate anatomical and clinical selection of candidate patients (10). The Harmony Transcatheter Pulmonary Valve by Medtronic is a self-expanding valve approved by the FDA in 2021–2022 for the treatment of severe pulmonary regurgitation in native or surgically repaired right ventricular outflow tracts, particularly in the context of repaired Tetralogy of Fallot and other congenital heart diseases. This valve was specifically designed for complete coverage of the right ventricular outflow tract and is available in TPV22 and TPV25 sizes, allowing adaptation to large and variable outflow tracts. It is mainly indicated for severe pulmonary regurgitation with a regurgitant fraction $\geq 30\%$ by echocardiography or cardiac magnetic resonance imaging, primarily in repaired Tetralogy of Fallot (71% of cases), pulmonary valve stenosis (21%), and other congenital heart diseases (8%) (2,3). On the other hand, the Melody

Transcatheter Pulmonary Valve is also a balloon-expandable transcatheter valve approved for percutaneous pulmonary valve replacement in patients with right ventricular outflow tract dysfunction involving failed bioprosthetic valves or circumferential conduits associated with moderate or greater pulmonary regurgitation and a mean right ventricular outflow tract gradient >35 mmHg. This valve consists of a bovine jugular vein mounted within a platinum-iridium stent and is available in two sizes: Melody TPV 20, with a 16 mm valve expandable up to 20 mm, and Melody TPV 22, with an 18 mm valve expandable up to 22 mm and potentially dilatable up to 24 mm without compromising valvular function. Its principal indications include failed pulmonary bioprostheses, repaired Tetralogy of Fallot, and dysfunctional right ventricle-to-pulmonary artery conduits (4). Finally, Myval Transcatheter Heart Valve is a new-generation balloon-expandable transcatheter aortic valve designed for transcatheter aortic valve replacement in patients with severe aortic stenosis. A distinctive feature of this valve is its 1.5 mm incremental sizing, instead of the conventional 3 mm increments, allowing more precise annular fitting. The valve is manufactured with a cobalt alloy metallic frame and is available in sizes ranging from 20 mm to 32 mm in 1.5 mm increments. It is designed to adapt to aortic annuli ranging from 270 mm² to 849 mm², enabling more precise device selection and thereby reducing the risk of significant oversizing or undersizing (5).

CONCLUSIONS

In conclusion, pulmonary stenosis and pulmonary regurgitation represent significant late complications in patients with previously repaired congenital heart disease, particularly in those with a history of repaired Tetralogy of Fallot. The present case corresponds to a 63-year-old female patient with a history of surgical correction of Tetralogy of Fallot and ventricular septal defect closure, who subsequently developed severe subvalvular pulmonary stenosis and moderate pulmonary regurgitation, presenting with progressive deterioration in functional class, dyspnea, syncope, and significant limitation of daily activities. Multimodal assessment through echocardiography and cardiovascular imaging allowed accurate definition of the severity and anatomical complexity of the right ventricular outflow tract, which ultimately guided therapeutic decision-making. Due to post-stenotic dilation of the pulmonary annulus and the main pulmonary artery trunk, percutaneous implantation of a balloon-expandable aortic-type Myval Transcatheter Heart Valve was selected, given the anatomical unsuitability for implantation of the Melody Transcatheter Pulmonary Valve. This case highlights the importance of a multidisciplinary approach, appropriate anatomical characterization, and individualized transcatheter treatment in patients with complex congenital heart disease, enabling

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symptomatic improvement and optimization of clinical outcomes.

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